

From meso to macro: homogenization of thermal properties in masonry systems

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Abstract. Homogenization of the thermal properties of masonry is crucial for building design, impacting thermal behaviour and energy efficiency. Understanding thermal behaviour is essential for assessing building durability. Existing models for simulating heat transfer in porous materials often focus on homogeneous materials, which do not accurately reflect the complex multi-layered structures in real buildings. Key factors influencing thermal efficiency include specific heat, thermal conductivity, and thermal expansion coefficients [1]. This study investigates the homogenization of thermal properties in brick masonry walls using different modelling approaches. It examines calcium silicate blocks and clay bricks for units, evaluating their performance under various weather conditions through meso and macro models. The study aims to enhance understanding of homogenization techniques and their effectiveness in improving masonry wall performance.

Numerical modelling

Homogenizing the thermal properties of masonry walls is essential for enhancing energy efficiency and durability in buildings. This study examines the thermal behavior of masonry walls constructed from calcium silicate blocks and clay bricks under different climatic conditions in Europe. Numerical modeling at the meso scale is used to analyze the thermal performance of these materials, and results are compared with homogenized models.

Description of the models

A one-leaf wall with a running bond is considered, focusing on the meso scale. The dimensions of the Representative Volume Element (RVE) are used to accurately simulate the masonry thermal behavior. Two types of masonry RVE were analyzed, first, the calcium silicate masonry model uses blocks measuring 18×19×33 cm with a mortar thickness of 1 cm. Secondly, the clay brick masonry model employs bricks sized 20×10×5 cm with a mortar thickness of 1 cm. Clay bricks are known for their excellent thermal mass and durability. In terms of material properties, the density of the brick and mortar is 2000 kg/m³ and 1350 kg/m³, respectively. In the brick, conductivity and specific heat are 0.5 W/(m·K) and 1000 J/(kg·K), respectively, whereas in the mortar, the values are 3 W/(m·K) and 800 J/(kg·K). For the block, the density is 1500 kg/m³, conductivity is 0.2 W/(m·K), and specific heat is 840 J/(kg·K).

Thermal Scenarios

Two different locations in Europe, Málaga (Spain) and Oslo (Norway), were selected to represent distinct thermal scenarios. A comprehensive review of weather data over the past ten years was conducted, focusing on two severe ten-day periods. Both temperature and radiation data were analyzed to model realistic environmental conditions. The thermal

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scenario for Málaga includes high temperature peaks and significant solar radiation. The thermal scenario for Oslo includes lower temperature ranges and moderate solar radiation compared to Málaga. Simulation parameters include a mesh size of 0.5 cm, a step size of 3600 seconds, and a total duration of 1033200 seconds.

Homogenization and comparison of the results

Homogenization is a mathematical process used to derive the macroscopic properties of a material from its microstructure [2]. In this study, weighted average method (WA) was used for the homogenization process. This was selected based on existing homogenization methods for masonry buildings. The results of the detailed meso models were compared with those of the homogenized models. Figure 1 illustrates this comparison, highlighting the differences and similarities between the two approaches.

Fig 1. Comparison of the thermal analysis in the RVE detailed brick model and homogenised model: (a) Malaga and (b) Oslo

The homogenized model provides an averaged thermal response curve for both Oslo and Málaga. Notably, the results for the clay brick masonry model in Málaga during high-temperature conditions show a closer alignment with the detailed RVE model. This suggests that the homogenized model effectively captures thermal behavior under specific conditions, but may require adjustments for different materials and climates.

The study demonstrates the importance of detailed meso-scale modeling in accurately predicting the thermal performance of masonry walls. While homogenized models offer a simplified approach, they may not always capture the nuances of thermal behavior in different climates and materials. Further research is needed to refine these models and enhance their predictive accuracy.

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References

1. Sýkora J, Šejnoha M, Šejnoha J. Homogenization of coupled heat and moisture transport in masonry structures including interfaces. *Appl Math Comput.* 219(13):7275–85 (2013)
2. Lourenço PB, Milani G, Tralli A, Zucchini A. Analysis of masonry structures: Review of and recent trends in homogenization techniques. *Can J Civ Eng.* 34(11):1443–57 (2007)